

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

ОЦЕНКА МНЕНИЯ МОЛОДЕЖИ ПО ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИМ ПРОБЛЕМАМ

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EVALUATING THE OPINIONS OF YOUTH ON ECOLOGICAL PROBLEMS

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Аннотация

В статье раскрываются взгляды молодежи 16-24 лет на экологические проблемы. Целью данного исследования является определение и оценка мыслей молодых людей в возрасте 16-24 лет, проживающих в Нахичеванской АР. Изменение климата приносит с собой множество проблем. Есть много вариантов решения этой проблемы. Это тренировки сознания и переживания, которые начались с детства. Многие исследования показали, что люди, заботящиеся об окружающей среде в детстве, более осознанно относятся к окружающей среде в более позднем возрасте. На самом деле, этот результат можно увидеть в этом исследовании. Данные были собраны методом полуструктурированного интервью. Исследование показало, что люди были осведомлены о таких понятиях, как экологическая осведомленность, изменение климата, глобальное потепление, и ни у одного из участников не было ответа об экологическом следе и экологической грамотности. Наконец, 90% респондентов заявили, что действующих законов и санкций недостаточно. Согласно полученной информации, на уровень их сознания влияет регион, в котором люди проводят большую часть своего времени, окружающие их учебники и издательские организации.

Abstract

The article elaborates the views of the youngsters at 16-24 about the ecological problems. The purpose of this study is to determine and evaluate the thoughts of young people aged 16-24 living in Nakhichevan AR. Climate change brings with it many problems. There are many options to solve this problem. These are the consciousness trainings and experiences that started from childhood. Many studies have shown that people who are environmentally conscious as children are more environmentally conscious later in life. In fact, it is possible to see this result in this study. Data were collected by semi-structured interview method. The study found that individuals were aware of concepts such as environmental awareness, climate change, global warming, and no participant had an answer about ecological footprint and environmental literacy. Finally, 90% of the respondents said that the current laws and sanctions are not enough. According to the obtained information, the region where individuals spend most of their time, the surrounding textbooks and publishing organizations influence their level of consciousness.

Ключевые слова: экологическая проблема, молодежь, мнение, изменение климата, социальное, химическое, глобальное потепление.

Keywords: ecological problem, young, opinion, climate change, social, chemical, global warming.

INTRODUCTION

It is all the environments in which humans and other living beings interact and carry out all their biological, chemical, social, economic and cultural activities. It can be seen that the environment, which is an indispensable place for living beings to live, is rapidly being destroyed due to wrong methods applied over time. This situation has become a danger to live today. If this insensitivity in environmental protection continues, the world will encounter more challenges and disasters. The main reason for these problems can be attributed to rapid industrialization. In addition, research shows that gaining this awareness in childhood has a positive effect on future generations.

Environmental problems are all phenomena that negatively influence the quality of life and behavior of

all living beings. Although many solutions have been suggested to prevent environmental problems, the most notable among them are the problems that should be prevented before they occur. To solve all these environmental problems, creating environmental awareness will be an important step. The world's population is growing rapidly. With the increasing population, the demands are also increasing day by day and various problems arise, including environmental problems. In modern conditions, it is impossible to consider human problems and environmental problems in isolation.

Today, the rate of urbanization has increased with industrialization and individuals spend most of their time indoors. With industrialization and the replacement of labor by machines, industrial societies began to form, which increased migration to cities. When people

realized that their health is affected by the air inside the building, they began to look for different solutions. Air quality in indoor environments is affected by interior items and furniture, materials used in the building, and solid and gaseous substances entering from outside. Pollutants in the air become dangerous and harmful to all living and non-living things when they exceed certain limits. If we look at recent years, the air quality in Turkey, one of the developing countries, has reached alarming levels. Industrial waste alters the quality of water, soil and air, which has harmful effects on living beings. In past years, most people lost their lives due to air pollution, and today air pollution can cause many chronic diseases.

Water is one of the elements necessary for living beings. The increase in production and consumption technologies causes environmental pollution [7]. As the need for usable and clean water is increasing day by day, water pollution is vital. Tumer notes that water pollution is a serious environmental problem not only for Turkey, which has a lot of fresh water and lakes, but for the whole world. Pandey attributes the reasons for the rapid pollution of water to increasing industry, sewage wastes and industrial junks from nuclear power plants. However, he notes that billions of people around the world do not have access to clean drinking water and are therefore exposed to many diseases. One of the causes of water pollution is pollution from agricultural sources. Dowd et al conducted a study in the state of California and found that many policies could be implemented at the local and federal levels. For example, the federal and state governments should work together towards a green policy [1].

The researcher emphasized the proposal about the creation of departments within administrative departments in direct coordination with environmental volunteers.

According to the report of the Ministry of Ecology and Natural Resources with the data of 2016, water pollution ranks first among the environmental problems. The report also mentions the causes of water pollution. These are industrialization, household waste, industrial effluent, fertilizer waste, agricultural spraying and fertilizing, unplanned urbanization. Although many problems are mentioned in the report, these are the most important issues.

It should be noted that many environmental problems have arisen due to industrialization and urbanization and it is important to take some measures in this regard. Every contamination can lead to further contamination. At this point, acid rains, erratic urbanization and the proliferation of social groups with a lack of environmental awareness, rapid water pollution can be examples, especially in places with dense coal deposits.

Although noise is considered along with all other environmental issues, it is either not mentioned at all in the books or only mentioned in general terms. Of course, from this point of view, the loudness and lowness of the noise is conventional depending on who perceives it and how it is perceived. Because what one perceives as noise may not be perceived as noise by others.

We did some measurements of noise pollution in

marketplaces and here are some of the results. As a result of the measurements, it was observed that there is more noise than expected on the market squares, especially in the evenings. As a result, they recommended solutions such as educating the public, parking cars in appropriate places to reduce noise, and building markets away from sensitive areas [3].

Our students also investigated the level of noise pollution in the mall and found that the noisiest parts of the mall were the children's playgrounds and the theatre. At this point, the researchers recommended separating the sections. In addition, noise pollution can cause many health problems such as insomnia. It causes attention deficit, social behavior problems, high blood pressure and psychological problems.

Another important problem for human life and environmental health is soil pollution. The soil is essential to life. Thousands of creatures live on even the smallest piece of land. People benefit from land in many ways. Due to factors such as urbanization, industrialization and city growth, land is overused and sometimes irretrievably lost.

When conducting a categorical analysis of soil pollution, common sources of pollution are discussed in 4 groups;

1. Industrial pollutants
2. Nuclear pollutants
3. Agricultural pollutants
4. Urban pollutants .

If soil degradation is not paid attention, exposure to organic pollutants, pesticides and heavy metals can result in what is known as a "chemical bomb" [4].

Climate change affects all living beings on earth in the past, at present and in the future and disrupts the balance of nature. Degradation of nature not only implies the change of all living beings who live in it, but also causes serious losses in biodiversity, ecosystem services, human well-being and health.

Today, almost all climate experts accept that there is change and disruption in the world climate system. With a general approach, climate change can be defined as long-term and slowly developing changes in climate conditions with global and very significant effects. Many national and global institutions, non-governmental organizations, central local governments and organizations are working in different ways and methods to accurately identify the changes and impacts that may occur in the climate so that people can live healthier and better lives.

Humanity has been encountering problems since the beginning of the world. These challenges are sometimes caused by the cycles of nature and sometimes by human activities. Almost all climate scientists agree that there is global climate change. It is considered certain that the climate changes due to global warming will occur as a result of the unconscious behavior and activities of people, which cause the disturbance of the balance in nature. According to many scientists, the forces that guide the changes in the global climate are the following; the greenhouse effect, the extent of changes in the accumulation of greenhouse gases, the effect of sulfate particles on the global climate and changes in solar radiation.

Climate change has been occurring in recent years with changes unknown to mankind. Climate changes, which affect all areas of life, also lead to radical changes in human habits. Weather is "all atmospheric phenomena experienced or observed anywhere on earth at any time". Climate is defined as "the synthesis of the average properties of all weather conditions experienced or observed over many years in any part of the earth, as well as the temporal distribution of their frequency of occurrence, observed extreme values, extreme events and all types of variability." It is clear that for centuries mankind has shaped its vital, basic needs such as shelter, nutrition and energy resources around climate and environmental conditions. Human health, well-being and planning are major issues affected by weather and climate. When we look at climate change, we can conceptually frame it by defining it as statistically significant changes in the average state of climate, or variability over a decade or more. Addressing climate change and environmental pollution is therefore critical to environmental health and academic reference.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

This research was conducted with the participation of 10 young people (3 females, 7 males) living in Nakhichevan who are students of Nakhichevan State University together with Karimli Abdulla and Aygun Kazimova who are the second year students of ecology who I am the teaching ecology. The youngsters were informed through research and participation was ensured on a voluntary basis. A phenomenological approach, one of the qualitative research designs, was chosen in the study. Therefore, while the phenomenological approach benefits from advantages such as focusing on a specific field and sector, concentrating on a specific city, appearing more authentic to the followers of the phenomenon, achieving higher integration rates and lower costs. Disadvantages such as a narrower sample will be considered as well. Qualitative research is a naturalistic research process that attempts to understand social phenomena in their natural environment. It focuses on the 'why' rather than the 'what' of social phenomena, using people's direct experiences as tools of meaning in their everyday lives. Instead of logical and statistical procedures, qualitative researchers study human phenomena, including biography, case studies, historical analysis, discourse analysis, ethnography, grounded theory, and phenomenology.

It uses multiple query systems for analysis. Phenomenology, on the other hand, is a type of qualitative research that focuses on answering the question of "what" rather than questions of frequency or magnitude such as "how much" Phenomenology is a psychological research method that sheds light on another dimension of phenomena that cannot be controlled by quantitative methods. As quantitative research methods are limited by the questions they can ask and answer, qualitative methods and phenomenology are limited to examining human experiences as they are consciously present. Therefore, phenomenology is not a substitute for or the opposite of quantitative methods, but instead works in conjunction with other research methods to more fully illuminate psychological phenomena.

Research data were collected through face-to-face interviews under the guidance of semi-structured interview method. The interviews were audio-recorded and notes were taken throughout the interview. During the assessment, young people's views on the concepts of climate, climate change, global warming and environmental awareness were taken into account.

The interview began with an explanation of the purpose of the study and the principles of confidentiality. First: "Where have you spent most of your life?" started with a question. After this question, they were asked if they lived in the village or city. Second, "What do you think environmental education is and how should it be?" the question was asked. The third question was "What do you think about climate change, what does it mean to you?" and asked for an explanation. Then: "When did the concepts of climate change and global warming first enter your life?" the question was asked. Then "What can global warming and climate change in our lives and what problems can they cause?" told and clarified. Regarding question 6: "What do you know about concepts such as ecological footprint and environmental literacy?" You asked to explain its significance. Finally: "What measures should be taken to improve national and international climate and environmental awareness, do you think that the existing law and awareness are sufficient?" A question was asked and the conversation ended with mutual thanks. A thematic content analysis was carried out in the study. Respondents' responses were directly coded and divided into groups. The coding process was carried out using the MAXQDA program. In the study, based on the non-disclosure of the identities of the participants, definitions such as N1, N2, ..., N10 were given instead of the identity data.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Looking at the results of the study, first of all, looking at the demographics of the study participants, 7 of the participants are male and 3 are female. At the same time, all participants are single. When considering the employment situation, it should be noted that 8 people are unemployed and 1 person is employed. When asked in which residential area they spent their lives, 6 answered in the village and 4 in the city. In the survey, responses to questions about individuals' thoughts on climate change were broken down into a few main themes and sub-themes. These main themes; "Living in the country", "Respect for the environment", "Climate change awareness", "Media", "Water scarcity", "Environmental literacy", "Political solution".

Village life

When checking the answers to the questions asked to find out the participants' attitudes towards climate change, the main topic of the research, it was found that 6 of the young people interviewed spent most of their lives in the village, and 4 of them lived in an urban environment. However, it should be emphasized here that all 4 participants who indicated that they live in the city emphasized that they go to their villages both seasonally and as part of their lives. Therefore, it can be said that almost all participants are attached to rural settlements where the environmental impact is relatively low.

"Since I was young I've spent most of my life in the city and partly in the country because I went to the village during the summer holidays." [N1]

"I lived mainly in the village, we raise cattle, we live together with plants and animals, so..."[N6]

Likewise, participants are aware of the congestion and problems caused by urbanization. Because all the answers received emphasize the "calmness" of village life. As can be seen from the answers to the first question, the first topic reached is "village life". In addition, sub-topics such as "relaxation through country life", "quiet", "clean environment" can also be called up.

Because if we look at the reference, Keeling and Whorf in their research found that people connected to rural life who move to urbans for certain reasons can go to rural areas. It is emphasized that they want to take short-term holidays, change the weather, clear their heads and calm down, use the countryside as 'natural' and see it as a getaway. Therefore, the feedback from the study supports the results of our study.

Respect for the environment

"What should environmental education be like?" to the participants. When examining the answers to the question, commonalities such as "think about the future", "do no harm to the environment", "put an end to irregular and unconscious constructions" emerge. As a result of the analysis of the coding of the answers, the main theme "respect for the environment" seems to be fulfilled. Because everyone involved sees the environment as a future outside of nature. In fact, it is stated in the answers given that this awareness is not provided by physical behavior but by said respect.

"People should actually respect nature. Let's take the simplest example, we shouldn't throw garbage on the floor, we shouldn't spit on the floor, we need to raise awareness of this issue. [N4]

Looking at the references, the study by Jones et al. that environmentally conscious segments take a much more holistic approach than personal space and are not myopic about environmental protection; They seem to meet in a world of long-term thinking. Therefore, the achievement of the Respect for the Environment theme shows that a positive result has been achieved in the first stages of climate change awareness.

Perception of climate change

Another question for the participants was "What do you think about climate change?" was the question asked. However, it should be emphasized that on this issue young people were more likely to be asked to explain climate change with their determination in their normal lives. In the answers to this question, the air temperature in our country in recent years has been outside the seasonal norms or the problem of rain and snow not falling on time is highlighted. Therefore, the participants reported that they could feel the climate change directly.

"So the water is already falling of what unknowingly causes climate change when the environment is polluted." [N3]

"In our country we already see that it is no longer snowing and raining like it used to be, so soil and productivity are declining. So we see the influence of all of them in our lives." [N7]

When the responses were coded, a common theme among participants listing the causes of climate change was the phenomenon of "rapid and unconscious industrialization." Because in its subtopics, dimensions such as "water pollution", "soil pollution", "air pollution" appear. Looking at the references, the study by Solomon et al. state that the general perception in societies about the causes of climate change seems to be an unconscious industrialization. Researchers emphasize the presence of carbon emissions, people's objections to some established industries, and particularly the proliferation of capitalist interests in their infrastructure, often shown in information and media. The answers given by young people on the subject of "industrialization" also confirm this idea.

"For example, a factory is built and trees are destroyed, so chemicals are produced..." [N2].

Media

Another question which the participants were asked was when the concepts of global warming and climate change came into their lives.

"I found out about 3-4 years ago thanks to the news." [N4]

"Our teachers have been teaching us this since elementary school. Many consciousness's have invaded our minds lately. Our people should gradually become aware."[N7]

All participants stated in their answers that these concepts were explained by their teachers in elementary school. But what's remarkable here is that they take it straight. Because news, social media and social projects come to the fore in the answers given by the participants. In other words, perceptions of global warming and climate change have been strengthened within the media theme. Indeed, Turkesh's research highlights that issues affecting the global world and society as a whole can be better addressed through popular media. Therefore, this determination is reflected in the responses of the participants [5].

Lack of water

When participants are asked about the problems caused by global warming and climate change, the issue of living water draws attention. Therefore, the main theme that emerged from the coding of the responses was 'water scarcity'. "With global warming, seasonal changes can occur. "In extreme heat, we can face problems like drought, fire and thirst." [N1] "There is a water problem, it's obvious, the water is being tapped." [N10] This finding is supported by Watson's emphasis that the entire balance in nature depends on water and that natural disasters only begin with water damage [6].

Environmental literacy

Another question asked to analyze participants' awareness of climate change related to the importance of terms such as ecological footprint and environmental literacy. Eight of the participants could not explain the concepts. On the other hand, 2 people gave similar answers to the previous questions about environmental education in general.

"After all, it is an issue that digitization will bring with it. As I said, if you give him a good education, the future generations will treat the children in school and the environment." [N2]

“As I said environmental awareness, we can combine all this with respect for nature, but

I don't know what you mean academically.” [N10]

At this point, a remarkable situation arises when examining the reference. McCulloch's research emphasizes that although there are many scientific studies on environmental problems, they are not so successful in reducing them to societies and enlightened societies [2]. When the answers from the interview were examined, it appeared that youngest people were not aware of these problems. Only 2 people tried to explain that they are aware of the environment. Other people said they had no information.

Political solution

In the last question, the participants were asked: "What measures should be taken to improve national and international climate and environmental awareness, do you think the existing law and awareness are sufficient?". In their responses, participants focused in particular on 'administrative' and 'political' solutions such as the inadequacy of legislation, creating green strategies, slowing down investment and strengthening energy policies. The main theme highlighted by the participants is therefore based on the "political solution".

“The existing awareness is not enough, at the international level I'm not sure if a specific department has been created for this issue, but as I said, something like environmental awareness, a general international federation, an organization can be created and transferred there and the money fund will be transferred there. Long-term investments should be made to prevent the mentioned climate changes. [N2]

"I don't think the existing laws are sufficient, but I don't know anything about them. Education is also given as social consciousness, but there is no one who implements it. Education is offered from elementary school, but some people throw garbage on the floor, for example. There are no sanctions." [N5] “Of course, individual awareness is not enough, but I don't know what can be done on an international level. I think that the existing laws are not enough." [N6]

The research reviewed shows that individuals believe that the climate is changing, they are concerned about the future and that both individuals and local governments have some responsibility at this point. The most important factor here is the presence of environmentally conscious people. In fact, people without environmental awareness create pollution that can lead to climate change and global warming.

CONCLUSION

The results obtained as a result of the research showed that young people have views on issues such as environmental awareness and climate change. 60% of respondents said they spend most of their time in villages or rural areas. We can talk about the positive impact of this situation on environmental awareness and love of nature. All respondents answered the question of how environmental education should be carried out, with the most common answer being “throw away the rubbish”. This was a predictable response given the damage seen from soil contamination. In fact, it's a topic we've heard a lot from teachers, mainstream news, and social media since elementary school. More than

half of those surveyed cited melting glaciers and declining rainfall as examples of “climate change.” 2 people said they have no idea about climate change and its impacts. Respondents stated that they had learned about climate change through 2 different channels. These are: teachers at school and television news media. Respondents' responses to possible climate change problems are very close together. Answers were collected on the topics of soil problem, water problem, deterioration of the body, change of seasons. All participants commented on our individual and social responsibility.

In the analyzes carried out on the topics, it should be emphasized that the central view of young people on the subject of global warming and climate change is that protecting the environment equals protecting the future. It is also evident from the answers given that young people say that they are directly feeling and observing climate change. The main topic of the solutions proposed by the youth are the political and legal guidelines to be developed. If one considers in the same way that the environmental awareness developed in young people is established more quickly via the media, it can be said that public awareness can be achieved primarily through visual and popular media.

PROPOSAL

Climate change has many impacts. Pollution caused by human activities can cause climate change. Gases from factories, the unconscious dumping of industrial waste into seas and swamps, and the result of unplanned urbanization are concentrated in chimneys. Gases released into the atmosphere and many other factors play important roles in climate change. In fact, it is possible to feel climate change today.

It is very important to take preventive measures before pollution occurs. Great responsibility rests with both individual and public administrators. Environmental education, take possession of nature, do not pollute the environment is the duty of mankind. It would be helpful to do research at this point to enlighten individuals. Research has also shown that people who are infected with environmental awareness at a young age are more sensitive to the environment and nature in the future.

Environmental awareness education should be included in the curriculum of students practically from elementary school. Research shows that children who grow up with nature will be more sensitive to the environment in the future. In order to form this awareness not only at school but also at home, cooperation between parents and school should be established.

Greater participation by children and young people in nature and environmental projects can be ensured. The activities can be carried out in cooperation with relevant non-governmental organizations. Youth centres, schools and local self-government bodies in the regions and villages should continue their joint activities.

In our country, new educational models can be integrated into the education system so that environmentally sensitive and responsible generations grow up from an early age. Appropriate conditions should be created in the school environment; it would make sense to increase outdoor activities. In addition, the number

of “forest schools”, which have many role models worldwide, should be increased. Cooperation with the state should take place for the necessary infrastructure and financing.

References

1. Dowd, B., Press, D., Huertos, M. (2008). Agricultural nonpoint source water pollution policy: The case of California's Central Coast. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 128(3) , 151-161.
2. McCulloch, S. (2006). Global warming threatens fisheries. *Times*. December 2006.
3. Stansfel, S., Matheson, M. (2003). Noise pollution: non-auditory effects on health. *British Medical Bulletin*, Volume 68, Issue 1, December 2003, Pages 243–257,
4. Stojic, N., Pucarevic, M., Stojic, G. Railway transportation as a source of soil pollution. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, Volume 57, December 2017, Pages 124-129.
5. Türkeş, M., (2004). Küresel İklim Değişikliği ve Olası Sonuçları. *Hava kuvvetleri Dergisi*, 348,70-77.
6. Watson, R. T. (2001). *Climate Change 2001*. Presented at the resumed Sixth Conference of Parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, Bonn.
7. Yılmaz, A. ve Yanarateş, E. (2020). Öğretmen Adaylarının “Su Kirliliği” Kavramına Yönelik Metaforik Algılarının Veri Çeşitlemesi Yoluyla Belirlenmesi. *Kastamonu Education Journal*, 28(3), 1500-1528, doi: 10.24106/kefdergi.722554.